

A REVIEW ARTICLE ON KUSHTHADI LEPA***¹Dr. Rajesh Krishna Nikam, ²Dr. Aditya Arvind Samant, ³Dr. Sudhindra A. N.**¹First Year P. G. Scholar, Department of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana GAM & RC. Shiroda, Goa.²Professor, Department of P.G. Students, in Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana., GAM & RC.³Professor & H.O.D., Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, GAM & RC.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Rajesh Krishna Nikam**

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ABSTRACT

Ever since life originated, every human being has been at risk of falling ill which made him to think about gaining health. For the same herbal, mineral and herbo mineral drugs were used as crude remedies.^[1] Ayurveda a traditional system of Indian Medicine, it is a holistic science Which deals with its fundamental principle and having various classical remedies on skin disease. Due to environmental changes, Life style changes, increasing work stress which directly affects health also many factors responsible for Skin disease are widely included in the heading 'Kushtha'. Here in this article we have tried to throw light on Kushthadi Lepa.

KEYWORDS: Kushtha, Skin Disease.

As the skin covers the external structure of the body, Lepa is considered best for the treatment of various types of Kushtha. Lepa are the external applications in the form of pastes (Kalka) or topical ointments for ailments of skin. Ayurvedic Acharyas have mentioned several lepa and various formulations are explained under Lepa kalpana for healthy beautiful and glowing skin.

INTRODUCTION

Kushtha a broad Spectrum skin disease, has been described by different Acharyas with slight differences. Any disease or diseases of twak are considered under 'Kushtha Roga' in Ayurveda. There are basically 2 types of Kushtha.

- 1) Mahakushtha^[7]
- 2) Kshudrakushtha^[11]

The prime symptom of any skin disorder includes discoloration, itching, burning sensation, loss of sensation etc. Any of these symptoms occurring as result of any of the Kushtha leaves the affected person in Discomfort, Disability leading to Death.

Though Several medications are available for the treatment of skin disease external application plays a very prominent role not only treating the physical appearance of skin but also provides Psychological Satisfaction for the Suffering person.

The lepa include the present day exploration in terms of therapeutics, cosmaceutics and neutraceutics mentioned in Schedule 1 of Drugs & Cosmetic Act 1940.

Classification of Lepa

According to Sushruta - 3 types Pratepa, Pradeha and Alepa.

According to Sharangadhara – 3 types Doshaghna, Vishaghna and Varnya

Pralepa:- It's application of lepa is in the form of thin layer (tanu) prepared from sheetvirya dravyas.

Pradeha:- It is applied as thick layer using ushnavirya dravyas beneficial in vatapradhan vyadhi.

Alepa:- It's the application of medicated lepa for Vrana-Shodhana, utsadana. Its combination of pralepa and pradeha.

Doshaghna:- It's the application of Lepa for the pacification of vitiated doshas in a thickness of 1/4 angulas.

Vishaghna:- It's the application of lepa for pacifying visha and is applied in the thickness of 1/3 angula.

Varnya:- It is applied in a thickness of 1/2 angula beneficial in pigment disorders as it imparts colour.

Preparation of Lepa

Generally for the preparation of lepa the drugs are finely powdered and then are made into Kalka form i.e. paste by adding liquid media like madhu, ghrita, taila,

gomutra or jala. It should be applied in pratilomagati.

कुष्ठ मुलकीज प्रियङ्गव सर्षपास्तथा रजनी ।

Kushthadi Lepa

Ref. of Kushthadi Lepa is available in Bharshajya ratnaral; and chakradatta.

एतत् केशरषष्ठ निहन्ति बहुवार्षिक सिद्धम् ॥ च.कु.चि.

Kushtha Mulaka Priyangu Sarshapa Haridra Nagkeshara

Composition of Kushthadi Lepa

	KUSHTHA	MULAK BEEJ	PRIYANGU	SARSHAP	HARIDRA	NAGKESHAR
Latin name	Saussurea lappa	Raphanus sativus	Callicarpa macrophylla	Brassica campestris	Curcuma longa	Mesua fera
Family	Compositae	Brassicales	Verbenaceae	Brassicaceae	Zingiberaceae	Clusiaceae
Ras	Tikta, Katu, Madhur	Tikta, Katu, Madhur	Tikta, Kashay	Katu, Tikta	Tikta, Katu	Kashay, Tikta
Virya	Ushna	Ushna	Sheet	Ushna	Ushna	Ushna
Vipak	Katu	Katu	Katu	Katu	Katu	Katu
Guna	Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna	Laghu, Tikshna, Sara	Ruksha	Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna	Ruksha	Laghu, Ruksha

Role of Lepa in Kushtha chikitsa

Bahiparimarjan chikitsa:- As Kushtha arises due to the vitiation of mainly vata, kapha and tridoshas Kushtadi lepa is mainly indicated to pacify the doshas that are vitiated locally. Acharyas stated that just like agni gets shanta after pouring water, Similarly vitiated doshas which are manifesting Kushtha also get pacified by application of Lepa, as the main Symptoms of Kushtha include pain itching, burning sensation (Ruk, Kandu and daha).

certain types of kushtha even without abhyantara aushadha prayoga. Hence Lepa kalpana is given utmost important not only in Kushtha chikitsa, but in Ayurveda as a whole. So many advancements in the Classical methods of Lepa kalpana are made now-a-days not only for therapeutic purpose but also gaining popularity in the branches of dermatology, cosmetology and nutraceuticals for much better and faster results adopting modern techniques and procedures to make it reachable to every individual.

The dravyas which are applied as lepa Causes Shodhang, Shophahara, ropan in particular lesion of kusita. Drugs in lepa are applied in prattloma gati i.e. direction opposite to hair follicles facilitates the faster and effective absorption of drugs active components into Skin thereby facilitating rapid relief of Symptoms as well as disease on the whole.

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Mode of action of Lepa:- Here Twak being the Site for doshas like Bhrajakpita, here samanvayu and vyanavayu performs activities dike penetration and absorption. Absorption of minute particles of drug takes place through pores or roma kupa Starts penetrating due to it's virya and prabhara.

Pathya pathya (Do's and Don't's)

The aim behind advocating Pathya pathya is to avoid recurrence of disease. Patient should avoid heavy Exercise, Over indulgence in sexual activity, Strenuous Work or fighting to Exhaust, excessive driving and heavy Meal including viruddha Aahar for 1 year offer recovery. The Causative factors are basically responsible for Agnimandya (Digestive process Supressant) and can further vitiate vata dosha, ultimately triggering pathogenesis of kushtha.^[4]

CONCLUSION

As kushtha takes the Bahya Rogamarge (Twak), Bahirparimarjana Chikitsa in the form of lepana helps the lesions efficiently when used along with abhyantar aushadha prayoga. Lepa alone has the efficacy to cure